

8T – Interacting Fields

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Abstract:

By analyzing the setting of the 8T and in particular the primordial coupling constants series under spin representation it is possible to construct a situation in which there exist an interaction among particles of different spin. That is by defining a spin operator and treating each coupling term as a combination of spins in ascending order.

Introduction

The 8T setting is a Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g)$, with (3,1) signature. The manifold is the connected manifold, invoked stationary, $s = s_0 \times \mathbb{R}$. The manifold has areas of extremum curvatures that remain as they are overtime, this are yielding time invariant acceleration from them on the metric tensor M, given by two conditions below (1). The reason for the acceleration in the 8T is that the manifold is a part of an infinite packet of universes, which interact at areas of extremum curvatures, as g is the Ricci flow, and as a result flatten each other metric tensor causing it to accelerate in a time invariant rate, given by equations (1.2) and (1.1). By (1.2A) those manifolds are topologically invariant. Flatness is an immediate result of this framework as given by the illustration below.

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \cap \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$$

$$\sum_{m=1}^{K/2} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_m} \frac{\partial s_m}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=1}^{K/2} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2.A)$$

The manifold experience arbitrary amount of net curvature isomorphic to prime numbers or the number one. That construction yielded the primorial coupling constants series presented in equations (1.4) to (1.43) present the first and second representation. I.e. net curvature on the matrix tensor and the prime critical line.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{1.4}$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \tag{1.41}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{1.42}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \tag{1.43}$$

For example, the Electromagnetic coupling term, we have proven the invariant three to be an electron by putting it in the fine structure constant formula:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.44)$$

We have described the arbitrary variations of the manifold by the term on the main equation:

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} \delta g' = 0 \quad (1.46)$$

We partitioned and discretized the arbitrary variation term and derived the existence of Fermion. In particular, we have shown that it must have an even amount of elements, which differ in sign and create nine threefold combination, and no more than two distinct elements.

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 \dots = \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i \quad (1.47)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (1.48)$$

In addition, with bosons, described by the term (1.49) as they were proven discrete amount of prime curvature on the matric tensor:

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0 \quad (1.49)$$

We have presented the spin classification in the 8T thesis, page seventeen, while using the prime critical line:

Spin 0: $2N_0$ variations

Spin $\frac{1}{2}$: $2N_0 + 3$ variations

Spin 1: $2N_0 + 3 + N_V$ variations

Spin $N = 2N_0 + 3 + N_{V1} + N_{V2} \dots$ variations

Let us analyze the idea of interacting fields. Instead of the spin classification presented above, we can consider the coupling terms as expressions that contain all the "fields" or the distinct kind of particles in the term itself. Those fields are not only interacting but generating each other in succession, in such way:

$$0 \rightarrow \frac{1}{2} \rightarrow 1 \rightarrow 2 \rightarrow \dots$$

In a certain sense, if we consider the Boson as a separate entity, it has spin one-half, but the invariant present of the majestic three then ensures that the Boson will summed as spin one. In other words the electron fields and the Boson fields are entangled in such way that is ensuring the spin of the Boson to be one. Since the primordial is time invariant, given by the invariance of the coupling terms under temporal shifts, so does this relation.

So now instead of the classification of spin we can represent each coupling term to be a mixture of spins of distinct kind. Define spin operator:

$$\mathcal{b}: [\mathbb{R}, \mathbb{Q}] \rightarrow \mathcal{S}_{[\mathbb{R}, \mathbb{Q}]} \quad (1.64)$$

That is a mapping between the integers and non-integer fields onto a spin operator in such way that the spin is matching the subscript:

$$\mathcal{b}: 0 \rightarrow \mathcal{S}_0$$

$$\mathcal{b}: \frac{1}{2} \rightarrow \mathcal{S}_{1/2}$$

$$\mathcal{b}: 1 \rightarrow \mathcal{S}_1$$

Now each coupling term can be represented in a way that reflect the idea of interacting fields, which are represented by spin operators.

$$[(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \rightarrow \mathcal{S}_0 + \mathcal{S}_{1/2} + \mathcal{S}_1 \quad (1.44.A)$$

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)

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